

Theranostics: A Dual Modality Approach for Targeted Drug Delivery and Real Time Disease Monitoring in Oncology

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Abstract: Despite of the availability of therapeutic interventions and supportive care, the number of cancer cases worldwide remains a major source of concern in terms of morbidity and mortality. The rise in cancer mortality may be attributed to shortcomings in the present diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. A new method called "Theranostics" has made it possible to precisely diagnose and treat cancer patients at the same time. Even though they are still in the early stages of development, theranostic agents—such as plasmonic nanobubbles, liposomes, radioisotopes, and quantum dots—can be attached to anticancer medications, cancer cell markers, and imaging agents. With the aid of current imaging techniques, these agents may make it easier to diagnose, treat, and manage cancer patients.

Theranostic is a precision medicine which integrates diagnostic nuclear medicine and radionuclide therapy for various cancers throughout body using suitable tracers and treatment that target specific biological pathways or receptors. This review covers recent theranostics of radio-immunotherapy for non-Hodgkin lymphoma, and treatment of bone metastasis using bone seeking radiopharmaceuticals. Furthermore, new radiopharmaceuticals for prostatic cancer and pancreatic cancer have been added. of particular, F-18 Fluoro-2-Deoxyglucose (FDG) Positron Emission Tomography (PET) is often used for the treatment, monitoring and estimating patient outcome. Theranostic's ground-breaking methodology, which promises better medication selection based on particular molecular aspects of disease, more predictive capacity for side effects, and new methods to objectively monitor therapy response, is the primary cause of its immense excitement.

Keywords: Theranostics, radio-theranostics, chemotherapy, cancer and prognosis.

Introduction

Cancer, also known as a malignant tumour, is one of the major diseases that threaten people's lives globally. Traditional tumour treatments mainly include surgical resection, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy. However, the unmarked remaining cancer cells after surgical resection easily metastasize, leading to postoperative recurrence. Moreover, chemotherapy and radiotherapy show a significant killing effect on both tumour and normal tissues. Besides, tumour cells are prone to developing resistance to chemotherapy and radiotherapy. [1]

Fig no. 1: Mechanism of Theranostic particle

Theranostics is a re-emerging new medical term of combination of diagnostic and therapeutic techniques using suitable drug combination. The aim of theranostics is to provide personalized medicine to patients with cancer by suitable radionuclide imaging and radiotherapeutics which targets specific biological pathways and receptors.[2] Theranostics, a new biomedical technology that combines diagnosis with therapy, has great potential in personalized cancer medicine, including real-time monitoring of the treatment process and reflecting the feedback of the therapeutic effect. Numerous theranostic systems combining different imaging techniques (e.g., magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), and photoacoustic imaging (PAI)) with diverse therapeutic methods (including chemotherapy (CHT), photodynamic therapy (PDT), photothermal therapy (PTT), and gene therapy (GT)) through one (imaging)-to-one (therapy), and many-to-many types have been developed [3]. The terms "multifunctional" and "theranostic," which were first used to describe the two-step process of diagnostic therapy for individual patients—first, testing for potential reactions to new medications, and second, customizing treatment based on test

results are frequently used to describe this combination of therapy and diagnostics in a single treatment.[4] The phrases multifunctional and theranostic (also known as theragnostic) are frequently used interchangeably at this still-emerging stage of the field's development, with no precise description of their possible distinctions. The majority of editorials, viewpoints, and reviews compiled in these issues would offer a highly optimistic perspective and answer to this query.[5]

Concept of Theranostics

Theranostics aids in the treatment of cancer and the management of other illnesses. Conventional chemotherapy and radiation therapy are key components of cancer treatment, where anti-cancer medications are absorbed by the cancer cells at a rapid rate of proliferation.[10] The disadvantage of traditional treatment is that the chemotherapeutic activity also affects healthy cells, leading to a number of adverse effects. The use of nanotechnology in nanomedicine, or the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases at the cellular and molecular level, can also be effective in the creation of therapeutic candidates that integrate diagnosis and treatment at the same time.[11]

Fig no. 2 : Theranostics particle targeting cancer cells

Theranostic nano-medicine integrates both diagnostic and therapeutic functions within a single nano-system, offering a powerful approach for early disease detection and targeted treatment, especially in cancer management.[12] These nano-medicines can be formulated using inorganic nanoparticles such as gold, silver, silica, and magnetic materials, or drug-delivery systems like liposomes, micelles, polymeric nanoparticles, and dendrimers.[13] They can carry both drugs and imaging agents, allowing simultaneous imaging and therapy. Compatible with conventional imaging techniques such as CT, MRI, PET, and X-ray, theranostic nanoparticles enhance diagnosis and monitoring. For example, iron oxide nanoparticles are used in MRI due to their magnetic properties, while quantum dots and porous silicon nanoparticles are used for in vivo fluorescence imaging.[14]

Nano-theranostics also enhance drug bioavailability, prolong circulation time, reduce side effects, and evade immune detection. They support multifunctional imaging and combined therapies like photothermal and radiotherapy for tumors. Beyond oncology, they are now being explored for cardiovascular diseases, such as using engineered nanoparticles with antithrombotic and photoacoustic properties for treating blood clots. [15]

Chemotherapy

The first successful and recorded application of systemic chemotherapy did not occur until the 1940s, but chemical treatment of cancer has been practiced for several centuries.[16] Nitrogen

Fig no. 3 : A patient receiving chemotherapy using Theranostics

mustard was utilized to treat a patient with lymphoma because of its harmful effects on the lymphatic system during combat. This event signalled the start of chemotherapy for malignant tumours, even if the tumour quickly returned after an initial strong anti-tumour effect.[17] Chemotherapy for cancer refers to the use of cytotoxic chemicals, or chemicals that have the ability to kill cells, in an effort to either completely remove the tumour, which may lessen the symptoms associated with the tumour and possibly extend its life. Most cytotoxic medications are administered intravenously.[18]

Chemotherapy as the main treatment modality for various cancers utilizes chemical drugs such as Doxorubicin (DOX), Camptothecin (CPT), Etoposide, S-crizotinib, 7-ethyl-10-hydroxycamptothecin (SN-38), Gemcitabine, and Paclitaxel to prevent the anabolism of nucleic acids, DNA replication, spindle formation, and protein synthesis. [19]

Few ways by which chemotherapy can be administered in our body:

Chemotheranostics

Despite their considerable effectiveness in slowing the growth of cancer, these modern clinical chemotherapeutic drugs have significant disadvantages, including poor high systemic toxicity, poor

medication absorption, and selectivity for cancer cells.[20] Some research teams have created activatable therapeutic compounds that combine chemotherapeutic medications with specific molecular optical reporters in order to address these issues.[21]The activatable theranostic compounds can specifically kill cancer cells when they interact with a variety of tumour-associated stimuli, such as a high level of reactive oxygen species, hypoxia, a highly expressed enzyme, acidity, and reduction. Additionally, a number of theranostic drugs based on molecules have recently been created with enhanced therapeutic effectiveness and reduced side effects. [22]

- i. Fluorescence imaging-guided CHT
- ii. Photoacoustic imaging (PAI)-guided CHT

Phototheranostics

Considering its characteristics of low systemic toxicity, outstanding temporal-spatial controllability, quick treatment, and minimal invasiveness, phototherapy—primarily PDT and PTT—has drawn a lot of interest in the treatment of cancer.[23]Generally speaking, PDT and PTT need the buildup of phototherapeutic chemicals at the tumour site followed by targeted light irradiation at the appropriate wavelength. Three essential components make up PDT: oxygen molecules in tumour tissues, an excitation light, and a photosensitizer.[24]When exposed to specific wavelengths of light, photosensitizers absorb NIR photons and transform molecular oxygen into deadly ROS, which causes oxidative stress and ultimately apoptosis in cancer cells.[25]

- i. Fluorescence imaging-guided PDT
- ii. Fluorescence and photoacoustic imaging-guided PDT
- iii. Chem-illuminescence imaging-guided PDT

Radiotheranostics

Radiotheranostics is the only theranostic category that has been incorporated into clinical practice. As seen above for ¹²³I and ¹³¹I iodide, or for targeted radiopharmaceuticals based on identical or comparable compounds labelled with either diagnostic or therapeutic radionuclides, it refers to the combination of radionuclide imaging and radionuclide therapy.[26] The structural components of radiopharmaceuticals vary and include chelators to coordinate the radionuclides, linkers to modify pharmacokinetics, and entities to target particular receptors or enzymes. Based on the radiation they generate, radionuclides are categorized as either therapeutic or diagnostic.[27] While radionuclides

that release β^+ particles or γ -radiation are beneficial for imaging, those that emit Auger electrons and/or β^- or α -particles can be employed for therapy. Some radionuclides, such as lutetium-177 and holmium-166, are mainly used for therapeutic purposes.[28]

Use of Nanoparticles in Theranostics

The development of new and creative nanoparticles for a variety of medicinal applications has expanded dramatically during the last few years. Despite significant issues with limited tumour absorption in various cancer applications, there are currently a number of intriguing alternatives that have been tested or are being developed.[29] However, before any NPs be translated into clinical application, their pharmacological and toxicological features must be thoroughly investigated. The presentation outlines the most essential general aspects of the NP alternatives, as well as their current level of utilization in the PCa and BC contexts. When possible, theranostic uses are brought up and briefly outlined for each type of NP. [30]

Iron Oxide Nanoparticles

Iron oxide particles, with diameters ranging from a few nanometers to approximately 100nm, have been evaluated and used in a variety of magnetic resonance technology-driven biomedical applications, including multifunctional theranostic complexes that combine tumour targeting, imaging, and cancer nano therapy in targeted cancer treatment.[31] Super-paramagnetic iron oxide NPs (SPIONs) are commonly utilized, with ultras-small SPIONs having a diameter of less than 20 nm. The last two are different allotropic oxidized forms of magnetite. Fe_2O_3 and Fe_3O_4 are popular in medical applications because to their low toxicity and excellent biocompatibility in humans. [32] The polymeric shell improves the stability of iron oxide nanoparticles (NPs) in solution while also allowing for the encapsulation of medicinal substances. Because SPIONs tend to aggregate due to magnetic, van der Waals, and/or hydrophilic/hydrophobic forces, it is critical to reduce this impact in biomedical applications using various surface modifications, such as PEGylation. [33]

Gadolinium, Manganese and Gold Nanoparticles

Gadolinium (Gd^{3+} , Gd (III)) has been used in various contrast media for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for many years because of its paramagnetic properties, ability to shorten the T1 relaxation time, and ability to cross a degraded blood-brain barrier.[34] The study of contrast media based on the paramagnetic element manganese (Mn^{2+} , Mn(II)) for MRI and NPs has just recently begun to gain traction. Carbon and Mn^{2+} NPs, for example, have been studied as MRI contrast agents, manganese enhance MRI during in vivo research, and functional MRI of the brain. Mn(II)-Au NPs have been studied for a variety of uses, including MRI contrast agents in stem cell labelling

and Prussian blue -based Mn(II) NPs as a theranostic agent with ultrahigh pH-responsive longitudinal relativity. In many various contexts, such as for PCa and BC, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) in the shape of nano-cages, -spheres, -beacons, -stars, -shells, -sheets, or nanorods are being assessed. [35]

Liposomes

Because of their special characteristics, liposomes are unquestionably the most well-known and adaptable of the several lipid-based nano-arsenals now on the market. They have many benefits, including low toxicity, sustained release of the therapeutics, biocompatibility, biodegradability, ease of synthesis, and the capacity to incorporate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic chemotherapeutic compounds.[36] They are made up of unilamellar lipid bilayers that envelop an aqueous core. Additionally, their surfaces can be altered for targeted cancer treatment. All things considered, liposomes' potential as a theranostic tool for cancer is probably going to be realized in clinical settings soon. [37]

Solid Lipid Nanoparticles (SLNs)

SLNs are spherical colloidal nanocarriers that have low toxicity and typically range in size from 50 to 100 nm. These particles were investigated for application in cancer theranostics. The solid lipid core is composed of fatty acids, triglycerides, etc. , relieved by an interfacial surfactant layer. To monitor PTT by imaging, for instance, Kuang and colleagues created IR-780 iodide loaded tumour vasculature targeted SLNs, which were selectively deposited at glioblastoma tissue. There aren't many papers that address the wide range of SLNs and their use in cancer for readers who are interested. [38]

Quantam Dots

Applications for Quantam Dots NPs are numerous, both in vivo and ex vivo. As Type II NPs, they have been used theranostically to target ligands and detect illness. When Gambhir and Cai imaged the $\alpha\beta3$ integrins of a U87 glioma model in vivo using PEGylated QDs with the RGD peptide, they found tumour to background ratios of 4.42 ± 1.88 at six hours, compared to 0.84 ± 0.21 for untargeted QDs.[39] Bhatia has demonstrated QD homing in cell culture using the F3 peptide, which binds nucleolin. The scientists showed that this siRNA was delivered to the nucleus by 50 nm QD incubation, and that the expression of the GFP gene was thereafter inhibited by 80%. Leaching of the heavy metal is prevented by encasing the CdSe core in a silica cover, which also reduces splenic uptake from 46.1 to 3.7% ID/g and liver uptake from 57.2 to 16.2% ID/g. [40]

Molecular Imaging in cancer Theranostics

In vivo molecular imaging is a technique that uses advanced diagnostic imaging equipment and systems to visualize, characterize, and measure biological processes at the molecular and cellular levels in humans and other living systems. Molecular imaging in the clinic allows doctors to look within the living body to diagnose illnesses, track their development, or provide molecular-level treatments. Instead of using *in vitro* or *ex vivo* biopsy/cell culture laboratory techniques, molecular imaging can study biological processes in their own physiological environment. [41]

The development of molecular imaging is anticipated to enable early cancer diagnosis, assess the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of recently created medications, and track the response to cancer therapy, forecasting the efficacy of a particular treatment before the anatomical size change detected by traditional diagnostic modalities like computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).[42]

Computed Tomography

The initial method of choice for cancer detection is CT, which measures X-ray absorption using material with a high atomic number (Z) to increase the sensitivity of CT images to certain contrast agents. This modality's benefits include accurate signal quantification, very high spatial resolution, fast scan periods, and inexpensive cost. Clinically employed CT molecular imaging agents include iodine, gold, bismuth sulfide, and composite ceramics made of iron oxide and lanthanide minerals.[43]

Most CT molecular contrast agents have a maximum number of X-ray-absorbing atoms that are integrated into a nanoparticle at the appropriate emulsions, such as polymeric nanoparticles, liposomes, and lipoproteins. For tumour bio-imaging, WS₂ nano-sheets may be employed as an X-ray computed tomography (CT) contrast agent.[44] When WS₂ nano-sheets coated with bovine serum albumin (BSA-WS₂) were administered to naked mice with HeLa tumours, the CT imaging showed distinct signals from WS₂ at the tumour site. According to recent reports, oxygen-deficient tungsten oxide WO_{2.9} nanorods show promise as a theranostic agent for simultaneous CT imaging.[45]

Magnetic Resonance Imaging

High soft tissue contrast and strong spatial resolution are two advantages of MRI over other imaging modalities. The first materials to be clinically approved for use as MRI contrast agents are

superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, or SPION.[46] SiO₂-coated SPION core-shell nanoparticles that have been tagged with an anti-CD146 monoclonal antibody and near infrared fluorescence (NIRF) dye may be utilized for MRI or NIRF imaging.

In order for malignant nodal activity to be detected by MRI, it was reported to regulate nodal signal intensity at the proper circulatory interval. This could make it a safer and easier staging agent for lymph nodes in prostate cancer. Injectable magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) improve MRI and offer a non-invasive, accurate way to measure the vascular volume fraction (VVF) in different xenograft murine models.[47]

Positron Emission Tomography

Positron emission tomography (PET), which provides quantitative imaging, is frequently utilized to diagnose anomalies at the cellular or molecular level. High-quality pictures are obtained for diagnosis using very precise radiopharmaceutical activity.[48] PET has a high sensitivity and specificity for monitoring biological processes. In a prostate cancer xenograft model, PSMA was conjugated to the copolymer DSPE-PEG maleimide, which spontaneously assembled into a homogenous multivalent lipid nanoparticle. The results showed that the targeted anti-PSMA scFv-LNP displayed enhanced tumour accumulation, which may support targeted therapy of this system in drug delivery. [49]

Ultrasound Imaging

Particle sizes employed in contrast agents to enhance contrast during ultrasonic imaging (USI) frequently surpass 250 nm. The USI contrast agents should be mentioned here even if the most widely used size definition for NPs is 1–100 nm. Both kinds of bubbles contain octafluoropropane gas, however Optison encloses the gas in an albumin-based shell and Definity employs a phospholipid spherical shell.[50] In NP-based US applications, SPIONs, liposomes, AuNPs, and nanodroplets have also been tested experimentally as drug carriers and contrast agents. Notwithstanding the well-established benefits of the US, it may cause drug release by inertial cavitation, which would harm the drug carriers mechanically. Unlike other stimuli like temperature, pH, and enzymatic degradation, US offered exquisite control over the spatiotemporal release and delivery of drugs into solid tumours.[51]

Optical Imaging

Optical imaging (OI) technology, also known as biophotonics, is a broad term that encompasses various forms of visible, ultraviolet, and infrared light. It also occasionally includes photoacoustic

(see above) applications in biomedical imaging. There are several intriguing publications about NP applications for both PCa and BC in OI technology. In general, an NP-based OI technique could optimize or enable an optical excitation energy, allow for multiplex imaging by utilizing numerous colour emitters for distinct targets at the same time; or provide multispectral imaging by combining spectroscopy and OI.[52]

Various applications of Theranostics

Theranostic is an emerging field of development in nanomedicines. It explains the developments in science to focus on more specialized therapies. It is a promising therapeutic paradigm involving diagnosis, drug delivery and monitoring of treatment response.

Theranostic gathers information from various biomarkers to prepare pharmaceutical formulations with greater efficacy and minimum toxicity. It has various applications including the management of various diseases and cancer therapeutics with the help of conventional radiotherapy and chemotherapy.[53]

Various applications of Theranostic are :

Pharmacogenetics :

- Pharmacogenetics deals about the individual variations in DNA sequences and responses to treatment interventions by the use of biomarker.
- This genotyping approach reduces the time and cost and increases the success rates
- It also involves variations in RNA and proteins that also have an important role in treatment.

[54]

Use in Targeted therapy –

Present-day treatment approaches frequently use the same regimen to treat the same ailment in various patients. Generally speaking, a small number of illness characteristics, including the patient's stage, symptoms, and physical state, determine the administration schedule and dosage of each medication.[55]

Dendrimers are particularly promising among the nano constructs that have been reported for use in biomedical applications because they can be synthesized more precisely with low polydispersity or mono dispersity to achieve the required in vivo pharmacokinetics for various applications by merely altering the generation.

For the goal of multipresenting different functional molecules, such as medicinal medicines, imaging reporters, or targeting ligands, dendrimers can offer hundreds or even thousands of sites if needed.[56]

Dendrimers' more definite and easily adjustable size and surface functions are the main benefits of using them for cancer imaging or treatment.

Conventional imaging methods have a low detection rate at PSA levels where targeted therapy with curative aim, like salvage radiotherapy, is beneficial in Prostate cancer with BR following main therapy. Numerous research points to the ability of ^{68}Ga -PSMA-PET to identify tiny LN metastases or recurrent PC that are ^{18}F -choline PET-negative.[57]

Use of Radio-theranostics :

The word “Radiotheranostics” has been derived from = Radiotherapy + Diagnostics. It uses paired radiopharmaceuticals - one diagnostic agent labeled with a gamma or positron-emitting radionuclide (for imaging, e.g. SPECT or PET scans) and another therapeutic agent labeled with a beta or alpha-emitting radionuclide (for targeted treatment). Both these agents target the same molecular marker, ensuring that the therapy goes exactly where the disease is.[58]

Radiotheranostics works by 4 mechanisms:-

1. **Target Identification** – Identifies a molecular target expressed by diseased cells (e.g. a receptor on a tumor cell).
2. **Diagnostic Imaging** – Injects the diagnostic radiopharmaceutical to visualize disease location and extent.
3. **Therapeutic Delivery** – Injects the therapeutic radiopharmaceutical that delivers cytotoxic radiation directly to those cells.
4. **Response Monitoring** – Repeats imaging to evaluate therapeutic effect. [59]

Radiotheranostics (also called theranostic radiopharmaceuticals) is an emerging field in nuclear medicine that combines diagnosis and therapy using the same or similar radioactive compounds targeting specific molecules in the body—usually cancer cells. Radiotheranostic uses are becoming more and more popular in cancer therapy and imaging. The introduction of therapeutic and diagnostic substances that have radically altered how we treat cancer is primarily responsible for this surge in interest.[60]

Additional factors driving the expansion of radiotheranostic applications include: first, the availability of data from several pivotal clinical trials that demonstrate the clinical benefits of novel diagnostic and therapeutic radiopharmaceuticals such as NETTER-1 , OSPREY , Ga-PSMA-11, VISION and TheraP ; second, the 2022 FDA approval of Lu-PSMA-617 for the treatment of

metastatic prostate cancer; third, the adoption of new technologies for early cancer detection and the availability of better therapies that improve both the response rates and OS of patients with cancer .[61]

²²³Ra-dichloride Radiotheranostics :

Men with castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC) and bone metastases experience a significant extension of both median overall survival (OS) and the time to skeletal complications due to the delivery of ²²³Ra-dichloride over multiple cycles.

Prior to the advent of ²²³Ra-dichloride, the radiopharmaceuticals used for treating bone metastases that targeted bones were usually β -emitters like ⁸⁹Sr-chloride and ¹⁵³Sm-ethylenediamine tetramethylene phosphonate (EDTMP).[62] These agents were typically given as a single infusion, resulting in pain symptom relief and enhanced quality of life (QOL). The action of ²²³Ra-dichloride is distinct from that of other radio-theranostic agents that target tumour cells directly: it mainly concentrates in regions where bone turnover is heightened—indicative of bone metastases—due to radium's resemblance to calcium, and the α -emitting ²²³Ra-dichloride then irradiates nearby cells, including those of the tumour.[63,64,65]

CHALLENGES FACED :

Various challenges of theranostics are –

Dosimetry :

- It takes time and effort to measure dosimetry accurately, and up until now, it hasn't been clear if dosimetry is necessary or valuable for optimizing the therapeutic activity-dose ratio in each patient. Given the basic variations in dose rate and processes of DNA damage, any extrapolation from external beam radiation will be incorrect, and dose calculations are complicated by the radiobiological consequences of radionuclide therapy at the cellular and molecular levels.[66]
- Effectiveness is frequently influenced by pharmacokinetics and repair mechanisms, as well as possibly by obscure immunologic and local inflammatory reactions, it may actually be preferable to think of radionuclide therapy as a tumor-selective treatment modality that is more akin to systemic chemotherapy. The potential use of poly ADP ribose polymerase inhibitors to obstruct DNA repair or combination chemimmuno-radionuclide therapy with radiation sensitizers are examples of dosimetric analysis.[67]
- It is difficult to obtain dosimetric data in individual individuals serially during the necessary time period due to the short half-life of ⁶⁸-gallium.

- Rigorous serial post-therapy dosimetric quantitative imaging is impractical for routine clinical use, but the recent advent of simplified single-shot quantitative imaging after PRRT may allow contemplation of measurement of dosimetry in every patient. A three-dimensional approximation of the dose distribution of ^{177}Lu -DOTATATE can be made by a single quantitative SPECT image at 4 days, with acceptable accuracy, and, with modification, may perhaps be extrapolatable to ^{177}Lu -PSMA therapy[68]
- The half-life of fluorine-18 is more convenient, and ^{18}F -PSMA-1007 PET/CT is presently being tested to provide repeated quantitative dosimetric imaging.³ The recently created ^{18}F -PSMA ligands may provide cost and availability advantages over ^{68}Ga , as well as dosimetry facilitation, as diagnostic accuracy is comparable to that of ^{68}Ga -PSMA PET/CT.[69]

Oncologist engagement in theranostics :

The challenge for those of us who want to practice therapeutic nuclear oncology is to treat patients more like physicians and work closely with our medical oncologist colleagues to manage cancer in a personalized way. [70]

Nuclear physicians also need to learn molecular oncology and become fluent in the new language of genomics and proteomics by attending intensive courses such as that conducted at the University of Ulm as a 2-year European Society for Medical Oncology accredited online course supplemented by 6 periods of 1-week of personalised onsite instruction. We must also understand the pharmacokinetics of the new radionuclide targeting agents and the radiobiology of their effector mechanisms, in order to work with our physicist colleagues to design practical dosimetric theranostic protocols for each of our patients.[71]

The idea behind personalized medicine is that by using molecular analysis of a patient's tumor, effective medications may be chosen to manage it and extend survival.[72]

Future Prospects

Several targeted agents tagged with ^{177}Lu have been shown to be clinically effective. The availability of high activity levels of ^{177}Lu , together with its excellent nuclear properties, has led to widespread interest in its clinical application. This radionuclide's long half-life provides logistical advantages, especially for countries with limited nuclear capabilities. Another important aspect is the ability to produce ^{177}Lu on a large scale from enriched ^{176}Lu with suitable specific activity and radio nuclidic purity using medium flux research reactors.[73] Future prospects for prostate cancer theranostics include extending its use to earlier stages of the disease, developing and testing new radiotracers and therapeutic isotopes, researching

combinations with other treatments such as immunotherapy, and optimizing existing therapies such as ^{177}Lu -PSMA and ^{223}Ra -dichloride. The idea is to make this individualized method more broadly available so that patients can have better outcomes.[74]

Future prospects for theranostics include major advances in targeted medicines, particularly those based on innovative radiopharmaceuticals such as targeted alpha-particle therapies and small molecules, which provide more precise and effective treatment with fewer side effects. The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) will be critical for individualized treatment by analyzing complex data to forecast results and improve dosages. Furthermore, theranostics is being investigated in combination with other modalities such as chemotherapy and immunotherapy, and its applications are growing beyond cancer to other disorders. [75]

Theranostics' future possibilities for combination therapy are quite promising, thanks to advances in customized medicine, nanotechnology, and artificial intelligence. The primary goal is to integrate theranostics with other therapeutic modalities to improve efficacy, overcome drug resistance, and reduce side effects. [76]

Conclusion

A theranostic tool is a single platform that combines therapeutic and diagnostic modalities to enable the simultaneous imaging and treatment of a disease. The creation of such a tool would transform the field of individualized healthcare by enabling patient-specific therapies to address the diverse character of many of our most debilitating illnesses.[77] By enabling each patient to get the appropriate amount of treatment to fulfil a predetermined, universal standard of health, this kind of tool would optimize treatment durations and resource allocation. The analytical chemist's combined instrumental and practical chemical expertise makes him or her a useful member of the project team, working with biologists, physicists, engineers, and medical experts.[78]

Injecting genetic circuits directly into patients rather than into their isolated cells—which is possible when the tissue can be reached directly—could also lower therapeutic costs and manufacturing difficulties. It will be crucial to keep an eye on how theranostic cells affect the surrounding tissue as they get more powerful.[79] For instance, integrating CARs into various immune cell types can alter the target cell's local microenvironment, which may be advantageous for the short-term therapeutic objective. Public awareness efforts emphasizing the safety and health advantages of therapeutic and diagnostic bacteria, together with positive branding, may help change public perceptions about the usage of modified cells.[80] Emerging as a substitute for current small-molecule medications and protein biologics, cell-based therapeutics have advanced quickly through clinical studies and

regulatory approval. More sensitive diagnostics and innovative treatments for illnesses that were previously untreatable will result from the growing cellular engineering toolkit.[81]

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